

Science Does Matter!

MATTER Undergraduate Research Journal Editorial Board¹

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Abstract

Undergraduate research is a critical and unique experience, especially for students who aim for future academic paths. There are undergraduate research publications like The Yale Scientific Magazine that date back to the 19th century. This historical viewpoint highlights the long-standing importance of undergraduate research across the world. International Undergraduate Research and Creative Activities (IJURCA), a journal, is an example of an international undergraduate research publication. This broadens the scope of undergraduate research and strengthens the universal nature of science. In line with METU's motto, "Research at METU begins at the undergraduate level," MATTER seeks to establish an undergraduate research journal in Türkiye and an area accessible to all undergraduate programs. The important thing is that undergraduate students carry out all the processes, and MATTER has an interdisciplinary research format. This underlines the pioneering influence of this journal in the Turkish academic environment. It is essential not only to conduct undergraduate research but also to publish it. Students can work on and even publish their ideas through undergraduate research programs. Students are inspired to carry out their study and publish it thanks to undergraduate research journals like MATTER. This review highlights the state of undergraduate research in the world and MATTER's perspective.

Keywords: undergraduate research, science, Türkiye
November 2023

1. Undergraduate Research in Türkiye and MATTER

MATTER, Türkiye's first undergraduate research journal, was published on November 30, 2013, by METU Metallurgical and Materials Engineering Department students with the support of department faculty member Prof. Y. Eren Kalay. The aim in those years was to ensure that undergraduate students had a platform to publish their research and, in this way, to prepare undergraduate students for graduate peer-reviewed publications.

The first and the following second issues of MATTER, published in 2015, accept submissions from undergraduate

MATTER cover page from 2013

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students working in metallurgy and materials research. As of its 3rd issue, published in 2016, MATTER has become interdisciplinary, with two articles published in the journal coming from the university's multidisciplinary design studio. This shift marked a significant expansion in the scope and reach of the journal.

In 2020, Middle East Technical University students came together to make MATTER ready for publication again. The editorial team brings together people from different departments and faculties, so MATTER ceased to belong to one field and became utterly interdisciplinary. Unfortunately, the journal could not be published due to the worldwide COVID-19 pandemic. Some of the editorial team also graduated during this period. One of the critical features of MATTER is that undergraduate students carry out the entire process. For this reason, a new team of undergraduate students was established in the summer of 2023. MATTER aims to create an undergraduate research journal in Türkiye and an area open to all undergraduate programs by supporting METU's mission of "Research begins at the undergraduate level." Although undergraduate research is conducted and supported in Türkiye, and universities in Türkiye have peer-reviewed journals that publish their scientific research, there is no example of a journal other than MATTER, which is published entirely by undergraduate students and only publishes articles by undergraduate researchers. This highlights the pioneering role of MATTER in the Turkish academic landscape.

2. Undergraduate Research in the World

Universities publish undergraduate research journals and magazines to encourage student's work, collaboration, and research at the undergraduate level. Some of them date back to the 19th century. The Yale Scientific Magazine (YSM) is the oldest college science publication in the United States of America, established in 1894 and still being published (Magazine, Y. S.- About YSM n.d.). This historical perspective underscores the long-standing value placed on undergraduate research globally.

The world's leading universities publish undergraduate research journals to promote research and the work of their undergraduate students. Those journals both include peer-reviewed and refereed ones. For example, SURJ (Stanford Undergraduate Research Journal) is the annual, peer-reviewed undergraduate research

The Yale Scientific Magazine

journal of Stanford University. SURJ was founded in 2001 and publishes research articles from all academic fields (About the Journal | SURJ: The Stanford Undergraduate Research Journal, n.d.). Another example of a peer-reviewed undergraduate research journal is MURJ (MIT Undergraduate Research Journal) from MIT (About MURJ - MIT Undergraduate Research Journal, n.d.). On the other hand, The Indiana University South Bend Undergraduate Research Journal (URJ) is a refereed, student-run publication whose editors are undergraduates (The IU South Bend Undergraduate Research Journal, n.d.).

Some undergraduate research journals worldwide are multidisciplinary, while some only publish in a specific field. For instance, the Undergraduate Journal of Psychology at Berkeley (UJPB) is an annual journal open to submissions from undergraduates who have finished their scientific studies in psychology and correlated subjects (Undergraduate Journal of Psychology at Berkeley, 2021). Another example is The Rose-Hulman Undergraduate Mathematics Journal, which only focuses on undergraduate research articles on mathematical science-related themes (Rose-Hulman Undergraduate Mathematics Journal | Rose-Hulman Institute

Indiana University South Bend Undergraduate Research Journal and Stanford Undergraduate Research Journal of Technology, n.d.).

One example of a multidisciplinary undergraduate research journal is The Harvard Undergraduate Research Publication (THURJ). Peer-reviewed undergraduate research from various fields, such as humanities, social sciences, and natural sciences, is featured in THURJ (ABOUT | Thurj, n.d.). The Columbia Undergraduate Research Journal (CURJ) serves as another example. Rigid multidisciplinary student research is showcased in the CURJ (About the Journal | Columbia Undergraduate Research Journal, n.d.).

In addition to university-based journals and magazines, there are also international undergraduate research journals. Such journals created an international dimension by accepting papers from universities and students worldwide. This both increases the universality of science and makes research at the undergraduate level more widespread. The International Journal of Undergraduate Research and Creative Activities (IJURCA) is committed to raising the profile and significance of undergraduate research worldwide. IJURCA published over 70 papers written by undergraduate students from more than 40 higher education institutions throughout its first ten years of publication (About the Journal | IJURCA | Central Washington University, n.d.).

The Harvard Undergraduate Research Journal

3. Undergraduate Research and Its Publication

Conducting undergraduate research might be considered a critical and unique experience, especially for students who aim for future academic paths. It will likely significantly improve student engagement and experience (Kaul et al., 2016). That might be the difference between theory and practice. Even though undergraduate students obtain the basics of research, conducting it is a distinct experience. The text on the paper is converted to an actual study. The learning is directly first-hand. In addition, it should be noted that different disciplines share different learning phases. However, in every field, students may concentrate on their research interests. Their research interest may significantly impact their learning, placing students in remarkable positions and giving them a chance for their graduate studies.

The value of conducting undergraduate research is indisputably high. Students receive many benefits, including developing new skills, comprehending new content, learning about research methodology, and the capacity for independent work (Kaul et al., 2016). However, there is another crucial element and a step related to conducting research.

It is publishing it. Researchers seek to find notable data or solutions to illuminate questions they have asked or asked by society. Publishing the research is essential in this sense. The research findings are vital and should be issued to provide data, recommendations, and solutions for current and future studies. A significant number of undergraduate students have broad ideas. Students can put their ideas to work and publish them via undergraduate research programs. Posting these ideas is the crucial part of this, as stated above. Publishing part might sometimes be the most challenging part of this process. Students are encouraged to conduct and publish their research, thanks to undergraduate research journals such as MATTER. As we witness the evolving landscape of undergraduate research, journals like MATTER symbolize the burgeoning academic potential at the undergraduate level and serve as beacons of inspiration for future scholars. They offer a unique platform where young minds can explore and develop their research skills and contribute meaningfully to the global body of knowledge. The journey of MATTER, paralleled by similar initiatives worldwide, is a testament to undergraduate research's increasingly pivotal role in shaping innovative and curious minds. Ultimately, these endeavors underscore the importance of nurturing young researchers whose fresh perspectives and novel ideas are essential for advancing science and academia.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, Matter, the first undergraduate research journal in Türkiye, aims to promote and highlight the value of undergraduate research. Also, the goal of MATTER is to establish an interdisciplinary research magazine that is available to all undergraduate programs. Undergraduate research may be considered an essential and distinctive experience, particularly for those students planning to pursue academic careers. Numerous advantages are provided to students, including the ability to work independently and the knowledge of research methods. But there is also another essential factor, which is publishing the research. Many undergraduate students have broad ideas. Students can work on and even publish their ideas through undergraduate research programs. Leading universities have also established peer-reviewed undergraduate research publications, emphasizing student research's significance in developing the next generation of academics and scientists.

5. Acknowledgments

Special thanks are extended to Prof. Y. Eren KALAY and Dr. İlhami BUĞDAYCI for their invaluable support and encouragement. Additionally, heartfelt gratitude goes to Zeynep Ege Uysal, Sabri Ufuk Arısan, Yasemin Zeynep Nar, and Servin Çağıl Ulusay, who played pivotal roles in the early stages of this issue and contributed significantly to shaping MATTER. Although they graduated before the culmination, their contributions remain integral to the essence of MATTER.

The undergraduate research journal MATTER received funding from AdımODTÜ*.

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